

Punjab/Delhi, India

Expert source: Rachel Spicer, The London School of Economics and Political Science

Entered by Ryan Johnson, University of British Columbia

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Entry tags: Sufism, Hinduism, Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Indic Religious Traditions

Punjab Region, India

Date Range: 1200 CE - 1600 CE

Region: Punjab, Rajasthan, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh & Delhi, India

Region tags: South Asia, India, Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh

28.5-32 degrees North, 74-77.5 degrees East.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Size and Structure

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Islam-Yes, mixture of devotional Sufi practitioners and more Mosque-centered Imams. Both supported by grants from growing imperial powers. Islam-Political elites, religious specialists (both more and less institutional), and non-elite.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Yes, period sees both a continuity of Brahmanical ritual with priestly leaders and growth of a more open field of devotional forms of religion. Hinduism- Political elites, religious specialists (both more and less institutional), and non-elite.